

Social management and social administration: a world perspective

Gestión social y administración social: una perspectiva mundial

Gestão social e administração social: uma perspectiva mundial

Revista Fundamentos ISSN 2545-6318 - Año 2024 N° 1 - Facultad de Ciencias Económicas - UNRC - Argentina

Flavio Ayres Marinho

Fundação Universidade Federal do Tocantins - Brasil

Contact: flavioayresm@gmail.com

Airton Cardoso Caçado

Fundação Universidade Federal do Tocantins - Brasil

Helga Midori Iwamoto

Fundação Universidade Federal do Tocantins - Brasil

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/10.5281/zenodo.12784599>

Abstract. Social Management has been developing in Brazil since the 1990's with the first attempt to delimit the term with Professor Fernando Guilherme Tenório in 1998. Currently it is a complex field with a large network of researchers that are part of the Network of Researchers in Social Management, besides having several periodicals such as *Cadernos de Gestão Social*, *Revista de Gestão Socioambiental* and annual meetings such as the *Encontro Nacional de Pesquisadores em Gestão Social*. This paper aims to compare the Brazilian perspective, which is assumed to be unique, with those found in the literature published in English through research on the *Periódicos Capes* portal under the terms 'Social Management' and 'Social Administration'. Therefore, it was possible to observe the originality of this area of studies as being a Brazilian perspective. Furthermore, it will make it possible to better develop this area of studies and possibly to expand this network of researchers internationally.

Keywords: Social Management; Social Administration.

Resumen. La Gestión Social se viene desarrollando en Brasil desde los años 90, con el primer intento de definir el término con el Profesor Fernando Guilherme Tenório en 1998. Actualmente es un campo complejo, con una gran red de investigadores que forman parte de la Red de Investigadores en Gestión Social. además de contar con varias publicaciones periódicas como *Cadernos de Gestão Social*, *Revista de Gestão Socioambiental* y encuentros anuales como el *Encuentro Nacional de Investigadores en Gestión Social*. Este artículo tiene como objetivo comparar la perspectiva brasileña, que se supone única, con la encontrada en la literatura publicada en inglés mediante una búsqueda en el portal *Periódicos Capes*, bajo los términos 'Gestión social' y 'Administración social'. De esta manera, fue posible observar la originalidad del área de estudio desde una perspectiva brasileña. Más adelante será posible desarrollar mejor esta área de estudio y posiblemente ampliar esta red de investigadores a nivel internacional.

Palabras clave: Gestión social; Administración social.

Resumo. A Gestão Social vem se desenvolvendo no Brasil desde a década de 1990, com a primeira tentativa de delimitar o termo pelo professor Fernando Guilherme Tenório em 1998. Atualmente, é um campo complexo com uma ampla rede de pesquisadores que fazem parte da Rede de Pesquisadores em Gestão Social, além de contar com vários periódicos como os *Cadernos de Gestão Social*, a *Revista de Gestão Socioambiental* e encontros anuais como o *Encontro Nacional de Pesquisadores em Gestão Social*. Este artigo tem como objetivo comparar a perspectiva brasileira, que se supõe ser única, com aquelas encontradas na literatura publicada em inglês através de pesquisas no portal *Periódicos Capes* sob os termos 'Gestão Social' e 'Administração Social'. Assim, foi possível observar a originalidade dessa área de estudos como sendo uma perspectiva brasileira. Além disso, possibilitará desenvolver melhor essa área de estudos e, possivelmente, expandir essa rede de pesquisadores internacionalmente.

Palavras-chave: Gestão Social; Administração Social.

Introduction

Overall, Social Management - SM is a new and promising science field, in progress, that seeks to enable a new way of public administration in opposition to Strategic Management, which is largely used in public and private institutions (Tenório, 1998). SM attempts to invert the logic State-Society and Capital-Labor in order to promote an administration that ensures people’s interests prevail, and thus, a fairer democracy is made possible.

This field of knowledge has been growing since Tenório (1998) acknowledge as the first paper regarding SM. Since then, the number of programs, cores of studies and laboratories which studies SM has been growing, presently there are some important examples such as: Study Program in Social Management from Getúlio Vargas Foundation (PEGS/EBAPE/FGV); Interdisciplinary Center for Social Development and Management from Federal University of Bahia (CIAGS/UFBA); Center for Social Entrepreneurship and Third Sector Administration from University of São Paulo (CEATS/USP); Center for Third Sector Administration Studies from Pontifical Catholic University of São Paulo (NEATS/PUC-SP); Interdisciplinary Center for Research and Studies on the Third Sector from Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (NIPETS/UFRGS); Interdisciplinary Laboratory for Studies in Social Management at the University of Ceará – Campus Cariri (LIEGS/UFC-Cariri); Center for Studies in Public Administration and Social Management from Federal University of Lavras (NEAPEGS/ UFLA); Interdisciplinary Center for Studies and Technologies in Social Management from Federal University of Vale do São Francisco (NIGS/UNIVASF); Group of Studies and Research in Social Management from Federal University of Tocantins (GEPGS/UFT) among others (Cançado *et al.*, 2015a).

Figure 1. Map of Brazil with the location of some Social Management Research Institutions

The objective is to identify in the English literature the meanings for the expressions “Social Management” - SM and “Social Administration” - SA and compare it with the Brazilian research tradition. This analysis is important for the development of this study field in Brazil and its possible connection with researchers from another countries. For example: work it was identified that in Spanish the terms *Gestión Social* and *Gerencia Social* (Hernández & Cançado, 2016), are polyphonic with dispersed meanings. These meanings that were found are different from the Brazilian perspective.

This work contributes with an analysis of a world perspective of SM and SA in the areas of Public Administration and Public Management. Beyond this introduction, it follows four sections. In the next, it is presented the Brazilian perspective, further on, the methodologic conception and path. Then, the results of this work were analyzed considering the Brazilian perspective and the final considerations.

Social Management: a Brazilian perspective

In this first part of this section, it is described the summarized path of how SM was developed until current definition. Subsequently, on the second part the main concepts that compose SM are discussed, formulating what is considered as the present definition used throughout this paper.

Origins of Social Management in Brazil

It can be said that SM in Brazil started with the first efforts of Tenório (1998) to define this field, which was done by him in 1998 when this author confronted strategic management with SM. Strategic Management is still the main theory adopted throughout Brazilian public and private administration. On SM perspective, it is needed to invert these pairs of words: State-Society and Capital-Labor to Society-State and Labor-Capital. The main character on these relations ought to be citizenship and not the State or the Capital forcers. However, what has been found so far are practices of a supposed SM more coherent with strategic management than with solidary and democratic societies (TENÓRIO, 1998).

Fischer (2002) suggested for Social Management, or Social Development Management, that it is a process of mediation that articulates multiple levels of individual and social power; It is a field of knowledge and space of hybrid and contradictory practices where cooperation does not exclude competition and vice versa. While being ethical and responsible, it should be efficient and effective; It is also a management of the networks, social relations, which are affected by people, behaviors, interaction capabilities and other subject human aspects; It is a process immersed in cultural contexts that shapes Social Development Management itself and at the same time are affected by it (FISCHER, 2002).

Following these propositions Fischer (2002) concludes:

The social management or social development management field is reflexive of the practices and of the knowledge built by multiple disciplines, designing itself as a pre-paradigmatic proposal, which is being formulated as research schedule and action by many research groups and centers in Brazil and abroad, as well by institutions of different natures that acts on local development (FISCHER, 2002, p.29).¹

From this statement, it can be perceived that SM is an interdisciplinary field, according to Fischer (2002), that has been growing nationally as well as internationally and at the same time is attempted in some institutions seeking local development.

Furthermore, Fischer (2007) affirms that, if management is understood as a function and not a tool, and as such it seeks to make society fairer, the distinction of organizations belong to the market, state or third sector spheres becomes irrelevant as all of them should be guided by the social aspect. Therefore, that is what must be admitted for understanding SM concept, here defined as a relational act capable of guiding and regulating processes by means of broad mobilization of actors on the communicative act resulting in intra and interorganizational partnerships. Therefore, decentralized and participative structures that seeks a good collective planned, viable, and sustainable (FISCHER, 2007).

Social Management is described by Carrion (2007) as a quest for new paths for the problem of social exclusion provoked by neo-liberalism. Consequently, it is not a simple matter as transposing the principles from business management to social field. SM seeks a local integrated development as well as financial and economical sustainability whenever possible. Aiming to achieve this proposal, it is a theory that recognizes the conflicts of interest between Society, the State and the Market (CARRION, 2007).

Moreover, the Carrion (2007) advocates that “The State” should be capable of ensuring local development by means of inclusive public policies, seeking administrative decentralization and supported on cooperation between the public sector, private sector and third sector. The greatest challenge of SM is to ensure these interactions are conducted based on solidarity. Some authors judge this theory as being utopian, such as Carrion (2007). This author argues that it is in fact a utopia, however, it is a proposition in construction, which seeks to build a more humanitarian society. No other paradigm can alter social morphology unless there is political will to do such, however, SM brings together tools and postulates capable of bringing change towards a more inclusive society (CARRION, 2007).

França Filho (2008) points that SM can be thought of on two perspectives. As a theory that identifies an issue of society or as a management process. On the first case, SM would be closer to public management. On the second, it would be related to a different way of management, which sees the social as an objective. Also, he adverts that SM needs to be careful with its banalization for everything that is not considered as traditional management is determined as SM (FRANÇA FILHO, 2008).

This author proposes two challenges for SM to overcome, as it follows:

In short, these two great challenges are imposed to social management. In one hand to overcome a traditional political culture that permeates the world of social organizations and to undertake effective partnerships between civil society and the public powers that recognize and stimulate the real potential of the affect groups, beyond a mere attitude of instrumentalization of action. On the other hand, the necessity of building a methodological framework that fulfills the basic requirements of a management truly engaged to social (FRANÇA FILHO, 2008, p. 6).²

Social Management, in opposition to strategic management, manifested its innovation potential. Different practices communities and strategic groups embraced this theory for without it they were scattered groups with no connection to each other. Therefore, SM brought them together giving them meaning and importance. However, this movement transformed SM as a process into a product, what halted its innovative capabilities (BOULLOSA & SCHOMMER, 2008; 2009).

According to Boullosa and Schommer (2008), SM can be thought as a way of managing, a management goal and management field of knowledge. At first, it can be defined as a management which has as its goal the social aspect, for a management which is not strictly economical. Thus, it can be defined as a way of managing originated in organizational and social contexts that do not belong to the market or to the State, but for a public non-state sphere of action in civil society (BOULLOSA & SCHOMMER, 2008; 2009).

However, these authors consider production on SM still insufficient, and, considering the fact it has become, according to them, a product instead of a process it risks losing its innovation potential, considering it imposes implementation rules. Boullosa and Schommer (2008) also states that even though much is discussed and studied regarding SM, few know exactly what it is about, who can perform it, who are the actors and professionals capable of doing it. Nonetheless, the authors suggest that the university management itself could be a good organizational environment for testing and further developing this theory and that formation on the area should articulate different knowledge areas and based on practical situations (BOULLOSA & SCHOMMER, 2008; 2009)

Araújo (2012) also considers SM suffered from an early institutionalization from the 20th to 21st Century. This author defends there are inconsistencies on the plural conceptions regarding SM, what is taught is not known by the lectures. It is needed, according to Araújo (2012), that first Management and Social are defined, in what shapes SM is different and how it intends to be innovative (ARAÚJO, 2012).

This author states that the social present in this terminology can be understood as both a public space of inter-relations and society itself. Therefore, it carries a native ambivalence that carries a group of paradigms and comprehensions. It has a clear goal, however, unclear practices and paradigms. Consequently, SM has as constituting elements plasticity, fluidity and hybridism (Araújo, 2012). On the author’s words it can be defined as:

As a way of management, it is a modality that presupposes a radical humanism, creativity and ethics. While a social object in order to face the contingencies between public and private on the consolidation of democracies, it refers to theoretical-methodological aspects regarding new organizational formats and new ways of

managing, highlighting the solidification and institutionalization (sometimes, early) of an epistemological and political-ethical field, that seeks to explain the relations and social processes (ARAÚJO, 2012, p.68).³

Araújo (2012) later concludes that considering this multiplicity of concepts, as well as some paradox practices, SM consolidates itself as a symbol of innovation, that, however, is no more than a new labeling which risks becoming no more than a 'small ethics. He also states that as previously thought, SM is way to which it is not known how to follow and thus, it is no way at all (ARAÚJO,2012).

For Pinho and Santos (2015) SM is a concept in progress, which is a statement upon which many authors agree. It can be said SM is not properly public nor private. On the construction of this term, the public is gradually shifted to collective, when related to values and possibilities of interactions. Most SM authors agree on the notion of it being a transparent process an of dialogic management in which participants seek mutual agreement (PINHO & SANTOS, 2015).

However, Pinho and Santos (2015) also criticize SM, appoint the National Meeting of Researchers in Social Management (ENAPEGS) as being a meeting of the area which, at the time, had been happening for 6 years and yet only 16% of the articles belong specifically to SM area. These authors also state that this theory is somewhat prescriptive with a strong utopic character considering Brazilian politics is still rooted in patrimonialism, whereas the politicians do not distinct public and private domain, setting personal above public interests (PINHO & SANTOS, 2015).

There are certainly practical experiences of deliberative democracy, however, according to Pinho and Santos (2015), they are still rare and scattered, thus, not enough to redefine national practices. Even though, it can be said there is a consensus when regarding to participation, it is a central aspect to SM and as such, not all participatory experiences are included in SM, but SM itself is based on direct participation (PINHO & SANTOS,2015; CANÇADO & PINHEIRO, 2014).

Cançado et al (2015) also consider that the term risk being trivialized and suffers from being confused with others such as politics management of social programs. However, it has been gaining recognition and visibility in both academic and media environments. Attempting to avoid this confusion, the authors sought to better outline the concept. For them, SM is composed of some basic characteristics: Collective decision-making, free from coercion, transparency, emancipations, anti-positivism and volunteerism (CANÇADO *et al.*, 2015).

Further on, Justen (2016), defines SM as an antithetic conception, in relation to strategic management - like Tenório (1998) who also proposed this opposition - which is based on collective decision-making, dialogicity⁴, language intelligibility, as a transparent process aiming emancipation. Justen's definition goes in accordance with Cançado *et al* (2015). Justen states that SM has as its final goal the Emancipation, following Freire's (1979 apud Justen, 2016) idea of dialogical pedagogy (JUSTEN,2016).

Thus, Justen (2016) then concludes that the right to dialogue is inalienable and should include all and any social relation. Only through effective, inclusive and plural participation, in conditions of being exercised with equanimity, subjects can be considered as 'occurrence subjects' (JUSTEN, 2016; FREIRE, 2011 APUD JUSTEN, 2016).

Additionally, SM seeks to subordinate instrumental logics to others more social, political, cultural or ecologic. It is not originally a management from the Market and State, it belongs mainly to the organizations. Although they frequently relate themselves to private and public institutions being a counterpoint to bureaucratic management in order to achieve common good in the republican perspective (França Filho, 2008; Cançado et al, 2015).

Theoretical Framework

Social management in a Brazilian perspective is described in theoretical categories. They are Self-interest properly understood – SIPU, Public Sphere and Emancipation. The relationship between SIPU and Emancipation in the Public Sphere happens by negative dialectics (Adorno, 1966/2003). This is the choice of this paper, the academic field in Brazil has other perspectives, but is the only one with a clear and direct proposal with this format.

The conception adopted and applied to this work is the one used, and created, by Cançado *et al.* (2015). These authors also consider that the term risk being trivialized and suffers from being confused with others such as politics management of social programs. However, it has been gaining recognition and visibility in both academic and media environments. To avoid this confusion, the authors seek to better outline the concept. For them, SM is composed of some basic characteristics: Collective decision-making, free from coercion, transparency, emancipations, anti-positivism and volunteerism (CANÇADO *et al.*, 2015).

The author gathers characteristics, which other authors associated to SM, being them: Deliberative democracy, dialogicity, emancipation, public sphere, self-interest properly understood, inter-subjectivity, rationality, solidarity and sustainability. Cançado *et al.* 2015 defines SM as:

In an effort of synthesis, we can define Social Management as: a dialectical process of the own social organization in the public sphere, founded in the self-interest properly understood and that has as a goal the emancipation of men (CANÇADO *ET AL.*, 2015, p. 178).⁵

Justen (2016) defines SM as an antithetic conception in relation to strategic management, which is based on collective decision-making, dialogicity, language intelligibility, as a transparent process aiming emancipation, and thus agrees with the definition of Cançado *et al.* (2015a), which is going to be further discussed ahead. Justen agrees with Cançado *et al.* 2015a. When stating that SM has as its final goal the Emancipation, for him following Freire's (1979 apud Justen, 2016) idea of dialogical pedagogy (JUSTEN, 2016).

Justen (2016) cites Freire (1979), who defends that emancipation can only be achieved in communion. This freeing is done, according to Freire (1979) by a critic and emancipating dialogue. Therefore, dialogicity is an essential character for emancipation. Furthermore, according to Justen emancipation is only achieved when the recipient of a given public policy is considered as a subject capable of thinking the world and thinking of himself in the world, such condition is therefore potentialized when in public spheres of dialogue (JUSTEN, 2016).

Moreover, this author also argues that before emancipation, inclusion is needed. Inclusion and plurality are only possible in an isonomic treatment where all human beings have equal value. Then, he concludes that the right to dialogue is inalienable and should include all and any social relation. Only through effective, inclusive and plural participation, in conditions of being exercised with equanimity, subjects can be considered as 'occurrence subjects' (JUSTEN, 2016; FREIRE, 2011 apud JUSTEN, 2016).

Justen (2016) then, concludes that:

The Social Management, this way, enables to identify the incompleteness of the economist perspective of sustainability, recognizing the nature of a living system, as well as a man, that, due to it, needs an approach in which the consequential utilitarian calculus is complemented by the capacity of '[...] thinking the world, thinking in the world, having a rational and calculating activity, but simultaneously putting in question yourself and your environment' (GAULEJAC, 2007). That, for sure, demands a dialogical, collaborative and communicative approach, something social management has to offer (JUSTEN, 2016, p.155).⁶

The Self Interest Properly Understood (SIPU) can be seen as a starting point for Social Management as it shelters two important aspects to be achieved which is solidarity and sustainability. This notion comes from Alexis de Tocqueville, author from the 19th century who wrote about the French Revolution defending individual freedom and political equality, whereas it is understood that the collective wellbeing is a condition for individual wellbeing. Additionally, it can only happen in a democratic context, which is reinforced by Social Management (CANÇADO, 2013; CANÇADO, RIGO, IWAMOTO & PINHEIRO, 2016). SIPU allows individuals to perceive the dynamics of their own performance on the building of the public sphere. Here, public sphere is where Social Management is built, it can be considered as an intermediate category on Social Management's process for it is the place and essential condition for its development (CANÇADO, 2013; MENDONÇA, GONÇALVES-DIAS & JUNQUEIRA, 2012).

According to Tenório (2005), the public sphere assumes equality of individual rights and discussion, without violence. The public sphere is the space where people present their inquiries by means of mutual understanding. Additionally,

the author affirms that civil society and public sphere are complementary in a way that the second is the space in which the dialogue between civil society and the state occurs (Tenório, 2005). Social Management, therefore, seeks to build a new public sphere in which the population is brought closer to politics, for it is a needed subjective space where it can be possible for people to deliberate about their needs and future. (CANÇADO, PEREIRA & TENÓRIO, 2015)

Other key concept in SM is participation, for it seeks a more participative, and dialogical management, in which the decisions are collective. According to Paula (2005), the societal public administration, inserted on the perspective of SM, manifest itself in alternative experiences such as Management Councils and Participative Budgeting (TENÓRIO, 1998; PAULA, 2005).

In the context of SM, oriented by Jürgen Habermas⁷ communicative rationality, the proposals from the participants cannot be validated without reaching an agreement, which must be achieved communicatively. Only if all participants, through the communicative action and dialogue, admits the validity of a given truth SM process occurs (TENÓRIO, 1998).

Participation and citizenship are, understood as the appropriation by individuals of the right to democratically build their own destiny. In Brazil, since 1960s, the social movements seek to develop social participation and to rethink Brazilian development through the optics of a new State management which ensures public participation in the institutions generation management experiences focused on the real demands of the people. Thus, SM is a societal alternative to substitute the technical and bureaucratic management in order to ensure participation by means of a decision-making process involving multiple social subjects (TENÓRIO, 2005; PAULA, 2005,).

For this participation to be effective, another key concept in SM is needed to be ensured: deliberative citizenship. It is understood as a political deliberative action in which an individual must participate in a democratic procedure, deciding in different parts and roles in society. It also means that legitimacy of political decisions must be originated in discussion processes guided by inclusion, pluralism, participative equality, autonomy and common good (TENÓRIO, 1998; TENÓRIO, 2005; CANÇADO *et al.*, 2015).

Deliberative citizenship is also inserted in the debate between liberals and republicans, where the second group seeks to negotiate what is best for the own group or society. Thus, it consists of taking in consideration the multiplicity of communication ways, moral, ethical, pragmatic and negotiations, in which all of them are ways of deliberating (TENÓRIO, 2005).

Emancipation, which is one of the main goals for Social Management, is here understood as freedom from oppressor domination based on the relations of production (TENÓRIO, 2002, 2005; CANÇADO, PEREIRA & TENÓRIO, 2015). Additionally, liberty, by means of emancipation, cannot be achieved individually, union and solidarity are needed. Also, the SIPU is reinforced by emancipation for when the human being is freed from manipulation the notion of being part of a society, for living in community, becomes clearer. Thus, making solidarity and sustainability more obvious (CANÇADO, PEREIRA & TENÓRIO, 2015)

All these concepts come together to compose Social Management and can be redesigned, following the Negative Dialectics logic, as many times it needs. There is intention of synthesis, only thesis and antitheses, and a permanent effort for improvement and change of this theory. Considering the Negative Dialectics theory, the concept is ephemerons, and here Social Management starts as an opposition to strategic management. However, Cançado, Pereira and Tenório (2015) draft a proper concept in order to avoid labeling everything that is not strategic management as Social Management, creating a concept which is also perceived as a non-concept. Picture 1 illustrates this relation (CANÇADO, 2013; CANÇADO, PEREIRA & TENÓRIO, 2015):

Picture 1. Social Management Main Theoretical Categories

Source: adapted from Cançado, Sausen and Villela (2013).

Methodology

The start point of this research are the papers that have the expression Social Management (SM) or Social Administration (SA) in the title. Other inclusion criteria are most cited papers and being available in the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES) Journals Portal⁸ (2018). Only the papers of the areas of Public Administration and Public Management were considered.

To find out the papers, it was used the Scholar Google search box inside the CAPES Journals Portal. Then, the papers with SM or SA in the title that had more than 10 citations were downloaded. It is highlighted that the papers that appeared as most cited but not available for free download inside the Portal were not accessed.

To analyze the papers, the method used was Content Analysis with open grid (Bardin, 2009). In this method, a table is elaborated, containing the main traits that characterize the papers. In this study specific case, the chosen traits were title, definition, summary and scholarly field.

Next, it was made a floating reading (Bardin, 2009) to identify the meaning of SM and SA inside the papers, in order to fill the cells of the table. By means of this identification process in the papers, it was possible to construct the corpus of words related to the ideas of both concepts.

Discussion, Data analysis and Results

Thirty-one papers were identified in the research according to the methodology adopted. During the analysis of the meanings of Social Management an additional classification was performed. The country or region that was the object of the paper was identified. This analysis was important because 16 articles (52%) are Chinese, and when considering only SA. There are 7 papers and 5 of them are from the United Kingdom (UK). The rest are distributed among other countries. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Means of Social Management in Public Administration Area

Meaning of Social Management	Paper Author(s) and Title	Country or Region
Closer to Brazilian Perspective	Adrianow, S. (1995). Social management and the applicability of British and French experiences to The Netherlands.	Netherland
	Hashi, A. A. (2011). Team Spirit and Collective Decisions in Social Administration from the Qur'anic Perspective: A Textual Analysis. <i>Journal of US-China Public Administration</i> , 8(7), 791-799.	USA
	Irwin, A., Georg, S., & Vergragt, P. (1994). The social management of environmental change.	Europe
	Xuan Dinh, B. U. I. (2016). The Role of Village Conventions in Rural Social Management at Present.	Vietnam
Government control over society	Ahmad, N. S. Y., & Halim, W. P. M. W. (2011). Administering social issues in Malaysia: An application of social management system.	Malasya
	Creemers, R. (2015). Cyber China: Updating Propaganda, Public Opinion Work and Social Management for the 21st Century.	China
	Dobrianov, V. (1984). Social indicators and social management.	Not identified (conceptual paper)
	Fulda, A. (2016). The logic and limits of the Party's social management approach in maintaining stability: lessons from Bismarck. In <i>China in the Xi Jinping Era</i>	China
	Liu, J. (2014). From social management to social governance: social conflict mediation in China.	China
	Novaretti, S. (2017). Social Governance vs. Social Management: Towards a New Regulatory Role for Social Organizations in China?	China
	Peng, O., & Li, M. (2014). The Social Management Innovation of "Two Dimensional Four Points" and "The Trinity"-Based on the Example of Chongqing Rural Human Resources Development.	China
	Pieke, F. N. (2012). The Communist Party and social management in China.	China
	Schlæger, J., & Jiang, M. (2014). Official microblogging and social management by local governments in China.	China
	Shuzhuo, L., Zijuan, S., & Feldman, M. W. (2013). Social Management of Gender Imbalance in China: A Holistic Governance Framework.	China
Yuwen, H., & Guangxing, S. (2013). Research on Online Public Opinion Management Mechanism Based on Social Management Innovation.	China	

Government Control Over Society Coming Closer to Brazilian Perspective	Bowen, W. (2014). Observation of Social Management from the Perspective of Micro-Blogging Politic.	China
	Bulmer, M. (1989). The British tradition of social administration: moral concerns at the expense of scientific rigor. <i>Sociological Practice</i> , 7(1), 21.	USA
	Cowling, M. (1982). Marxism and social administration: a shaky start. <i>Critical Social Policy</i> , 2(6), 6-13.	The U.K.
	Culyer, A. J. (1981). Economics, social policy and social administration: the interplay between topics and disciplines. <i>Journal of Social Policy</i> , 10(3), 311-329.	The U.K.
	Fewsmith, J. (2012). 'Social Management' as a Way of Coping with Heightened Social Tensions.	China
	Roberts-DeGennaro, M., & Packard, T. R. (2002). Framework for developing a social administration concentration. <i>Journal of Teaching in Social Work</i> , 22(1-2), 61-77.	The U.K.
	Smith, G. (1985). Dimensions of the 'crisis' in social administration. <i>Sociology of Health & Illness</i> , 7(2), 260-268.	The U.K.
	Wenyan, J., & Chengshui, L. (2013). Research on the Social Management Innovation Under "Legal Guarantee".	China
	Wu, F., & He, J. (2013). Capacity Development of Civil Society Organizations: Towards Inclusive Social Management in China.	China
Management of Social Public Policies	Bin, W., & Lei, H. (2013). Social Management in China in the 21st Century: Trouble and Breakthrough Based on the Different Management Subject.	China
	Chuanli, H. (2014). Functional relationship model-based research on participation of non-government organization in social management innovation.	China
	Ma, G., Zhang, T., & Nabi, G. (2016). Practices, Policies and Prospects of Social Management in China: A Study based on "Shidu" Elderly People.	China
	Terziev, V., & Georgiev, M. (2017). Active Social Programs Development in Bulgaria: Contemporary Challenges and Social Management Instruments.	Bulgaria
	WARHAM, J. (1972). Social and public administration. <i>The British Journal of Social Work</i> , 2(2), 229-232.	The U.K.
	Wei, M. (2013). The Social Management and Development Approach of Urban Minority: "Boundary-Crossing" and "Cultural-Sensitivity".	Not defined
Others (Scientists careers in Public Management)	Wenk, E., & Wenk, E. (1995). Making waves: Engineering, politics, and the social management of technology.	USA

Source: Developed by authors.

The results show 5 categories and the bigger is the Government Control Over Society with 11 papers. China is the most important country in this cluster with 9 papers (82%). Most of these papers presents SM as a method of public administration where the state prevails over the individual. Most of the authors describes the state as regulating society and concentrating decision-making powers for the government officers. The meanings of Social Management in this category are completely opposed to the Brazilian approach.

Other important result is the category "Management of Public Policies" with 6 papers. The papers show different ways to do this management, by the government directly or by the NGOs (Non-Government Organizations). China is represented with 3 articles (50%). This interpretation of Social Management was used in Brazil and Latin America in the 1990s and was overcome at the beginning of this Century (CANÇADO, PEREIRA & TENÓRIO, 2015).

Another interesting result is the possible changing in Chinese perception of Social Management coming closer to the Brazilian Perspective. Four articles (44%) of category Government Control Over Society Coming Closer to Brazilian Perspective are Chinese studies. These papers show possibilities of greater participation of the population in public

decisions. However, some authors state that this increase in popular participation is restricted to the discourse. The government proposes local councils to solve and discuss local problems. However they control these, so they end up following the wishes of the state rather than what is decided within the councils.

Also interesting are the papers belonging to the U.K. in this category, SA is depicted here as a science field studied in universities, which is used by the government to deal with economic and social issues as well as with public policies, being it an interdisciplinary field, coming closer to what public management is in Brazil (Bulmer, 1989; Culyer, 1981; Smith, 1985). However, it still excluding the other actor such as third society and the people itself.

The articles with the meaning closer to Brazilian perspective represents 13% (4) of the total. None of them is Chinese. It is interesting to identify closer the exact approach of these papers and others in another research.

Final Considerations

It is important to analyze Social Management meanings in different languages as so to strengthen the perspective adopted as being exclusively Brazilian, and therefore to show the importance of studying and developing this field as to value a national growing theory that can help our development and perhaps expand overseas.

Interestingly most of the papers, from Chinese origins, approach Social Management as a way of controlling society, managing conflicts by means of a top-down administration where the state is central. Some discuss a possible shift for a more inclusive administration where local population is included, however Novaretti (2017) states that this is limited to the discourse. In fact, people remain without power regarding decision-making processes. Others discuss the partnership between government and NGOs to manage social problems, which is a perspective similar to what happened in Brazil in the 1990s.

Finally, there are a few closer to what is considered Social Management in the Brazilian perspective. However, they are a very small number and not completely similar to our perspective. These approach collective decision-making, third sector participation, however none meet all the criteria: collective-decision-making, without coercion, based on intelligibility and transparency, moving towards the emancipation (CANÇADO, PEREIRA & TENÓRIO, 2015). Therefore, studies like this are pivotal to reinforce the importance of continuing studies in this area in order to strengthen this perspective, considering it is rather unique and originated in this country.

Notes

- 1 Translated by the authors
- 2 Translated by the authors
- 3 Translated by the authors
- 4 According to Soares (2023) "Dialogicity can be understood as an educational process that emerges from the participation of its agents. One assumes the determination to promote a sharing of issues and knowledge, so that each participant, educator or student, can broaden their horizons and advance in their understanding of the world"
- 5 Translated by the authors
- 6 Translated by the authors
- 7 German philosopher whose theory of communicative action originated the concept of Social Management itself.
- 8 <https://www-periodicos-capes-gov-br.ez1.periodicos.capes.gov.br/index.php>

References

- Adorno, T. (2003). *Negative dialectics*. Routledge.
- Adrianow, S. (1995). Social management and the applicability of British and French experiences to The Netherlands. *Netherlands journal of housing and the built environment*, 10(1), 27-44.
- Ahmad, N. S. Y., & Halim, W. P. M. W. (2011). Administering social issues in Malaysia: An application of social management system. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(22), 9224-9230.
- Araújo, E. T. D. (2012). (In) consistências da gestão social e seus processos de formação: um campo em construção.
- Bardin, L. (2009). Análise de conteúdo, Edições 70, Lisboa. *Portugal, LDA*, 288p.
- Bin, W., & Lei, H. (2013). Social management in China in the 21st century: Trouble and breakthrough based on the different management subject. *Public Administration Research*, 2(2), 73.
- Bowen, W. (2014). Observation of Social Management from the Perspective of Micro-blogging Politic. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 5(6).
- Boullosa, R. D. F., & Schommer, P. C. (2008). Limites da natureza da inovação ou qual o futuro da gestão social. *Encontro da Associação Nacional de Pós-Graduação e Pesquisa em Administração*, 32.
- Boullosa, R. D. F., & Schommer, P. C. (2009). Gestão social: caso de inovação em políticas públicas ou mais um enigma de lampedusa. *Encontro Nacional de Pesquisadores em Gestão Social*, 3, 65-92.
- Bulmer, M. (1989). The British tradition of social administration: moral concerns at the expense of scientific rigor. *Sociological Practice*, 7(1), 21.
- Cançado, A. C. (2013). Gestão social: um debate para a construção do campo. *NAU Social*, 4(6), 191-209.
- CANÇADO, A. C., Sausen, J. O., & VILLELA, L. E. (2013). Gestão social versus gestão estratégica. _____. *Gestão social e gestão estratégica: Experiência em desenvolvimento territorial*. Rio de Janeiro: Ed. da FGV.
- Cançado, A. C., Pereira, J. R., & Tenório, F. G. (2015^a). *Gestão social: epistemologia de um paradigma*. Curitiba: CRV, 2ª Edição;
- Cançado, A. C., Pereira, J. R., & Tenório, F. G. (2015^b). Fundamentos teóricos da gestão social. *DRd-Desenvolvimento Regional em debate*, 5(1), 4-19.
- Cançado, A. C., Rigo, A. S., Iwamoto, H. M., & Pinheiro, L. S. (2019). Gestão social, autogestão e gestão democrática pela Navalha de Occam: uma abordagem conceitual baseada na teoria dos conjuntos. *NAU Social*, 10(18).
- CARRION, R. M. (2007). Gestão social: especificidades e práticas em discussão. *Tecnologias de gestão: por uma abordagem multidisciplinar*. Vitória: EDUFES, 2, 108.
- Chuanli, H. (2014). Functional relationship model-based research on participation of nongovernment organization in social management innovation. *Computer Modelling & New Technologies*, 18, 771-775.
- Creemers, R. (2015). Cyber China: Updating Propaganda, Public Opinion Work and Social Management for the 21st Century. *Public Opinion Work and Social Management for the 21st Century (December 2, 2015)*. *Journal of Contemporary China*, Forthcoming.
- Cowling, M. (1982). Marxism and social administration: a shaky start. *Critical Social Policy*, 2(6), 6-13.
- Culyer, A. J. (1981). Economics, social policy and social administration: the interplay between topics and disciplines. *Journal of Social Policy*, 10(3), 311-329.
- Bui, X. D. (2016). The Role of Village Conventions in Rural Social Management at Present. *Vietnam Social Sciences*, 2(172), 34-48.
- Dobrianov, V. (1984). Social indicators and social management. *Social Indicators Research*, 14, 313-331.

- Fewsmith, J. (2012). 'Social management' as a way of coping with heightened social tensions. *China Leadership Monitor*, 36(6).
- Fischer, T. (2002). *Gestão do desenvolvimento e poderes locais: marcos teóricos e avaliação*. Casa da Qualidade.
- Fischer, T. (2007). O futuro da gestão. *HSM Management*, 10(64), 1-15.
- França Filho, G. D. (2008). Definindo gestão social. *Gestão social: práticas em debate, teorias em construção*. Fortaleza: Imprensa Universitária, 1, 26-37.
- Fulda, A. (2016). The logic and limits of the Party's social management approach in maintaining stability: lessons from Bismarck. *China in the Xi Jinping Era*, 71-96.
- Hashi, A. A. (2011). Team Spirit and Collective Decisions in Social Administration From the Qur'anic Perspective: A Textual Analysis. *Journal of US-China Public Administration*, 8(7), 791-799.
- Rivera Hernández, A., & Cardoso Cançado, A. (2017). ANALISIS DE LA GESTIÓN SOCIAL BRASILEÑA A TRAVÉS DE LA TEORÍA DE LA DECOLONIALIDAD. *Amazônia, Organizações e Sustentabilidade (AOS)*, 6(1).
- Irwin, A., Georg, S., & Vergragt, P. (1994). The social management of environmental change. *Futures*, 26(3), 323-334.
- Justen, C. E. (2016). O Angelus Novus emoldurado à gestão social: reflexões acerca da construção de políticas públicas emancipadoras. *Desenvolvimento em Questão*, 14(36), 135-157.
- Liu, J. (2014). From social management to social governance: social conflict mediation in China. *Journal of Public Affairs*, 14(2), 93-104.
- Ma, G., Zhang, T., & Nabi, G. (2016). Practices, policies and prospects of social management in China: a study based on "Shidu" elderly people. *J Publ Adm Govern*, 6(1), 87-103.
- Mendonça, P. M. E., Gonçalves-Dias, S. L. F., & Junqueira, L. A. P. (2012). Gestão Social: notícias sobre o campo de estudos e práticas a partir das interações e debates do VI Enapegs. *Revista de Administração Pública*, 46, 1391-1408.
- Novaretti, S. (2017). Social Governance vs. Social Management: Towards a New Regulatory Role for Social Organizations in China?. *Opinio Juris in Comparatione*, 1, 1-30.
- Paula, A. P. P. D. (2005). Administração pública brasileira entre o gerencialismo e a gestão social. *Revista de administração de empresas*, 45, 36-49.
- Peng, O., & Li, M. (2014). The Social Management Innovation of "Two Dimensional Four Points" and "The Trinity"-Based on the Example of Chongqing Rural Human Resources Development. *Asian Social Science*, 10(10), 219.
- Pieke, F. N. (2012). The Communist Party and social management in China. *China Information*, 26(2), 149-165.
- Pinheiro, L. S., & Cançado, A. C. (2014). Participação popular e instrumentos institucionalizados de participação em nível local. *Administração Pública e Gestão Social*, 19-26.
- de Pinho, J. A. G., & dos Santos, M. E. P. (2015). Gestão social: uma análise crítica de experiências brasileiras. *Revista do Serviço Público*, 66(2), 257-279.
- Roberts-DeGennaro, M., & Packard, T. R. (2002). Framework for developing a social administration concentration. *Journal of Teaching in Social Work*, 22(1-2), 61-77.
- Schläger, J., & Jiang, M. (2014). Official microblogging and social management by local governments in China. *China Information*, 28(2), 189-213.

- Shuzhuo, L., Zijuan, S., & Feldman, M. W. (2013). Social management of gender imbalance in China: a holistic governance framework. *Economic and political weekly*, 48(35), 79.
- Smith, G. (1985). Dimensions of the 'crisis' in social administration. *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 7(2), 260-268.
- Soares, E. S. (2023). Dialogicity as an educational practice with significant social implications: A workshop with indigenous teachers and their demand for a numbering system. *Prometeica-Revista de Filosofia y Ciencias*, (27), 356-365.
- Tenório, F. G. (1998). Gestão social: uma perspectiva conceitual. *Revista de administração pública*, 32(5), 7-a.
- Tenório, F. G. (2005). (Re) visitando o conceito de gestão social. *Desenvolvimento em questão*, 3(5), 101-124.
- Terziev, V. (2018). Active social programs development in Bulgaria: contemporary challenges and social management instruments. *IJASOS-International E-journal of Advances in Social Sciences*, 4(12).
- WARHAM, J. (1972). Social and public administration. *The British Journal of Social Work*, 2(2), 229-232.
- Mu, W. (2013, May). The Social Management and Development Approach of Urban Minority: "Boundary-Crossing" and "Cultural-Sensitivity". In *2013 International Conference on Public Management (ICPM-2013)* (pp. 215-220). Atlantis Press.
- Wenk, E. (1995). *Making waves: Engineering, politics, and the social management of technology*. University of Illinois Press.
- Wenyan, J., & Chengshui, L. (2013). Research on the social management innovation under "Legal guarantee". In *2012 First National Conference for Engineering Sciences (FNCES 2012)*.
- Wu, F., & He, J. (2013). Capacity development of civil society organizations: Towards inclusive social management in China. *A policy research paper prepared for the Governance for Equitable Development Project*.
- Huang, Y., & Song, G. (2013, May). Research on Online Public Opinion Management Mechanism Based on Social Management Innovation. In *2013 International Conference on Public Management (ICPM-2013)* (pp. 29-35). Atlantis Press.